

ISic3248

I.Sicily inscription 3248

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Estella Kessler,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [][Oc]tavius T(iti) f(ilius)[---]
2. [Co]rnelianus v[ixit]
3. [annis] XXII mens(ibus) I[[]
4. [T(itus)Octavius][---] charmo[---]
5. [et][---]ꝰpendu[sa]
6. [pare]ntes [fec(erunt) h(oc)] m(onumentum) s(ive) s(epulchrum) [---]

Apparatus

Text from Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Octavius Cornelianus, son of Titus, lived for 22 years and (?) months. Titus Octavius ... and Spendusa, the parents, made this. This monument or tomb ...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493978

EDR 139170

EDCS 22200398

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2004.0651

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 114

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